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FIERCE

*Feminist movements
revitalizing Democracy in Europe.*

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D6.2 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation progress report 1

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

EC	European Commission
EP	European Parliament
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
Mx	Month x
REA	European Research Executive Agency
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The dissemination, exploitation and communication of the project constitutes a pivotal aspect of its overall planning, due to its role on promoting FIERCE's intentions, scope and contributions to the target audience. The project adopts a multifaceted and detailed dissemination plan from the very beginning in order to:

- Raise awareness about the FIERCE project and the respective theoretical and practical tools to be developed throughout its implementation.
- Increase engagement and encourage involvement of the target groups in the project activities.
- Promote exploitation and sustainability of the abovementioned tools and best practises after the project's completion.

The present deliverable describes the progress and provides statistics of the dissemination and communication activities, both online and offline from the commencement of the project until February 2024 (M7-M18) reflecting the results of actions taken by the Consortium Members. Additionally, it provides an overview of the respective exploitation and sustainability activities of the project. This is the second version of the Dissemination and Communication Activities report, a deliverable that is scheduled to be conducted three times throughout FIERCE's duration (M6, M18 and M36).

The chapters below feature data regarding the website and the social media channels created for CALIPER, the networking activities of Consortium Members and all the additional actions taken to promote the project and its scope (i.e., press releases, newsletters, videos and interviews).

1. Introduction

1.1. The FIERCE Project – Summary

FIERCE aims to provide sound theoretical and practical knowledge and tools to revitalize alliances between the feminist movement, civil society and political decision makers in a context of growing social inequalities, political disaffection and strengthening of populist radical right anti-gender actors and discourses. The research uses an interdisciplinary, multi-dimensional and multi-level framework, that aims to overcome the limitations of both disciplinary scholarships and nationalist methodologies. FIERCE develops in-depth understanding of feminist and anti-feminist/anti-gender movements, activities and discourses, and their impact on the institutional arena and on policy outcomes, focusing on the period 2010-2021. These actors, and especially the feminist movement, will be studied through frame analysis, political ethnography and Social Network Analysis on the background of key gender debates and controversies prefigured to be situated in the areas of: labour market; health and reproductive rights; LGBTQ+ rights; migration; and gender-based violence. FIERCE will cover eight case studies (France, Italy, Greece, Slovenia, Turkey, Denmark, Poland, Spain) representing a wide variety of country contexts in socio-political, geographical and welfare terms. FIERCE moves beyond a country-based approach and provides a cross-cutting comparative analysis of the way debates and controversies on gender have influenced the dynamics and output of the policy process. Building on co-creation methods and on a strong alliance with civil society organisations, FIERCE proposes pilot actions that can reinvigorate democratic practices, in line with feminist inclusive visions for the future of democracy. FIERCE thereby sets out a bottom-up, problem-driven and impact-oriented approach, bridging academic knowledge, policy-making and bottom-up democratic strategies.

1.2. WP6 - Objectives

WP6 (Dissemination, Communication, Sustainability & Exploitation) aims to:

- Raise awareness and maximise the visibility of FIERCE achievements among the key target groups;
- Facilitate sharing of knowledge inside the Consortium;
- Implement FIERCE's communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy, activities and materials;
- Plan and verify the exploitation potential and added value of all exploitable outcomes during and after project's end;
- Build and engage a community of stakeholders;
- Establish synergies with relevant clusters, projects and initiatives.

1.3. The Deliverable 6.2

1.3.1. Purpose and Scope

The deliverable D6.2 "Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation progress report 1" showcases the overall progress of the Work Package 6 (WP6 - Dissemination, Communication, Sustainability & Exploitation) for the period March 2023 (M7) to February 2024 (M18) with emphasis on the activities performed, lessons learnt based on the defined dissemination and communication planning (see D6.1).

1.3.2. Target Audience

This report has both internal and external target audiences. Internally, it is aimed at all project partners to further develop/implement their individual and collaborative activities, as well as to identify needs and re-adjust the communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy.

In addition, the document can be used as a guide and practical tool for dissemination managers of on-going and future projects, who may be willing to explore the FIERCE strategy, as well as a reference point for the reviewers of the European Commission.

1.3.3. Structure of the Deliverable

The deliverable is structured into the following sections:

- Chapter 1 introduces the project scope, the WP6 objectives, the document's target audience, the relationship to the other work packages and the structure.
- Chapter 2 presents an overview of the reported communication and dissemination activities implemented throughout the addressed period.
- Chapter 3 presents updates on the project's exploitation and sustainability plan.
- Chapter 4 completes the report with a conclusion that comments on the overall actions.
- The Annex section includes an overview of the relevant KPIs of the present deliverable.

1.3.4. Relation to other WPs and Deliverables

The activities presented in this deliverable draw from and feed back into the overall actions of the project. In particular, the dissemination, communication and exploitation of FIERCE is directly related with WP4 and WP5 as it contributes to the wider disseminations and engagement of the respective audience (feminist organisations, collectives, activists etc.) to participate especially to the project's co-creation activities. This is the second report concerning the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. The third report will be conducted at the end of the project (August 2025, M36).

2. Reporting of the Communication and Dissemination activities (M7-M18)

2.1. FIERCE Website

The [FIERCE website](#), one of the key tools for the communication and dissemination of the project, went live on October 2022 (M2), successfully achieving the Milestone 11.

During this reporting period (M7-M18), the “[Resources](#)” subpage, which pertains to the project's results, has been enriched with additional content. In particular, resources available within dedicated sub-categories include: the project [promotional materials](#) in English and partner languages, project-related [blogs](#) documenting progress and findings, newsletters, [press releases](#), [podcasts](#), and [publications](#) prepared by our partners. Additionally, all public [deliverables](#) will be accessible on the “Resources” subpage upon approval by the EC.

In addition, the “[Clustering](#)” subpage showcases all the EU-funded projects related to the FIERCE topics and have received funding under the same Call for proposals under Horizon Europe (4 in total). Through communication with representatives from these projects, our website displays their brief project description, their logos, and online links.

The “[News](#)” presents all updates worth sharing with the public concerning the project's progress and the partners’ achievements.

Website Analytics

Using the “Google Analytics 4” tool, we have access to a detailed overview of traffic to the FIERCE website. This tool enables tracking not only visitor numbers but also other relevant quantitative information for users who visit the project website.

The following figures showcase online metrics for the project website for the period between March 2023 (M7) and February 2024 (M18).

Users

Figure 1: Website Analytics M7-M18

According to the figure above, over 2,000 users have reached at least one of the pages on our website during the aforementioned reporting period. According to information extracted from the official [Help Center](#) of the Analytics tool, by the term “Users”, we refer to the number of people who engaged with our site within the specified date range. Additionally, the “New users” metric indicates the number of people who have never visited our site before within the specified date range. The “Average engagement time” refers to the exact time users spend on our webpage, which is over 1 minute, indicating that people are spending some time engaging with our content.

Demographics

Figure 2: Demographic analytics M7-M18

According to the figure above, a list of the countries that most users come from is depicted. It is evident that traffic comes to our website not only from our partners’ countries but also from countries around the world, showing the outreach of the website beyond the countries of the directly involved parties.

Page views

Figure 3: Page views M7-M18

The statistics depicted in the figure above represent the total number of pages viewed on our website. Between March 1st, 2023, and February 12th, 2024, nearly 8,000 page views were recorded, indicating the genuine interest of our audience in the FIERCE content.

2.2. Social Media and online channels

Social Media play a key role in the communication and dissemination of the project, as they have the advantage of reaching multiple audiences and raising awareness about the project's progress. Key content promoted includes project-related news, blogs, press releases, newsletters, publications, videos, and more. Additionally, we extend our social media activity to showcase our partners' dissemination efforts and achievements within the project's context. Furthermore, we promote content related to project topics (i.e. Gender Equality Week) through reposts from reputable accounts such as [The European Institute for Gender Equality](#) (EIGE), [UN Women](#), the [European Parliament](#) and other recognized entities for gender equality.

These channels provide a space for networking. In particular, interactions with our "[sister Projects](#)" have offered us the potential to expand our reach through reshared content. Partners' organizational and personal accounts also play a crucial role in further promoting our content through resharing. To facilitate easy resharing, partners' organizational accounts are tagged in each FIERCE post. Additionally, external organizations are mentioned when necessary and available. The official account of the European Research Executive Agency (REA) is strategically mentioned in selected posts, such as upcoming events of our project, to enhance post reach through resharing.

To "catch the reader's eye" and make our posts more attractive for engagement, our posts are accompanied by a tailored graphic or visual banner featuring the FIERCE logo and the EC disclaimer.

The official social media channels of the project were established at the project's outset. Currently, more than 800 people follow our accounts across various social media platforms, with the number increasing daily. In order to monitor the monthly progress of the social media accounts, a dedicated excel file has been created to record the monthly statistics of our social media activity, using the analytics tools provided by the platforms used.

The sections below provide a detailed overview of the performance of each of the social media platforms used for FIERCE.

2.2.1. Facebook

The [Facebook page](#) of the project currently has 211 followers by (M18) February 2024, while the current report is being conducted. During this reporting period, 86 posts have been posted to the project's Facebook page.

Facebook reach (3.800 users in total for the period in concern) refers as "the metric for distribution of the content produced, including posts and stories". It also includes reach from other sources, such as tags, check-ins and page or profile visits. Reach is only counted once it occurs from both organic and paid distribution. This metric is estimated.

Figure 4: FIERCE Facebook analytics (M7-M18)

In addition, the FIERCE followers have performed more than 3 hundred interactions with the content. Facebook documents posts' interactions taking into account all the likes or reactions, saves, comments and shares made by users minus the number of deleted interactions. Simultaneously, nearly seven thousand impressions have been recorded. As described, impressions are the number of times any content from your Page or about your Page entered a person's screen. These metrics encompass the monthly tracking conducted by the T6.1 leader, who aggregates the monthly statistics.

The following figure presents the total number of profile visits in the Facebook page (left side) during March 1st (M7) to February 16th (M18), while the current report is being conducted.

Figure 5: Visits in the Facebook page (M7-M18)

The following figure presents an overview of the demographics of the Facebook page. As shown in the figure, women represent the majority of the audience, approximately 2/3 of the total amount. While people from all ages follow our profile, the age group 25-34 shows the most interest.

Figure 6: Demographic analytics for the Facebook FIERCE page M7-M18

The following table summarizes the statistics mentioned above.

Followers (in total)	211
Posts	86
Reach	3.800
Interactions	320
Impressions	6468
Profile Visits	993

Table 1: Summary of Facebook statistics (M7-M18)

2.2.2. X (Twitter)

The X (Twitter) account of the project, [@Fierceprojecteu](#), has a total of 202 followers during this reporting period. During M7-M18, there have been posted one hundred posts.

Based on the analytics provided, our X profile has reached an estimated 14,4 thousand impressions within the covered period. X defines the impressions as the aggregate number of instances that a tweet appeared on their feed.

Figure 7: Screenshots from all the “Impressions” reports provided by X Analytics M7-M18

The following table summarizes the statistics mentioned above.

Followers (in total)	202
Posts	101
Impressions	14.000

Table 2: Summary of X (Twitter) statistics (M7-M16)

2.2.3. LinkedIn

The LinkedIn page of the project, [FIERCE](#), has accumulated a total of 303 followers.

Based on the analytics aggregated by the platform for the period reported in this deliverable, the FIERCE posts have reached approximately 12 thousand impressions, which is defined as the views of the post in users’ screens.

Figure 8: “Impressions” statistics for the LinkedIn page M7-M18

In addition, the content posted during this period has collected more than three hundred reactions. LinkedIn platform counts the reactions’ number by all the user clicks, such as likes, comments and shares.

The following table summarizes the statistics mentioned above.

Followers (in total)	303
Posts	92
Reactions	328
Impressions	12.019

Table 3: Summary of LinkedIn statistics (M7-M18)

2.2.4. Instagram

The Instagram page of the project, [@fierceproject_eu](https://www.instagram.com/fierceproject_eu), currently counts almost 100 followers. During this reporting period, the Instagram page has attained 177 reaches, according to the insights provided by the platform.

Figure 9: Instagram Analytics (M7-M18)

In addition, there have been recorded 277 profile visits as shown in the following figure.

Figure 10: Instagram profile visits

The following table summarizes the statistics mentioned above.

Followers (in total)	95
Posts	20
Profile visits	277
Reach	117

Table 4: Summary of Instagram statistics (M7-M18)

2.3. Social media campaigns

2.3.1. Campaign on the International Women’s Day

On the occasion of the International Women’s Day on March 8th, the FIERCE consortium launched in March 2023 (M7) a social media campaign focusing on a topic related to the combination of women's empowerment and democracy. Specifically, the campaign aimed to highlight the historical moments

when women in each country of our FIERCE partners were granted the right to vote in elections, emphasizing that such democratic rights were not always granted, especially for women.

The implementation procedure began with the T6.1 leader informing partners about the campaign's concept. Partners from each country responded positively, providing information about the timeframe when women first voted in their respective countries. This information was used to create eight different posters representing the eight project countries (Denmark, Greece, France, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, Turkey).

From March 8th to March 10th, 2023, all posters were published on the project's online channels. The following figures demonstrate some of the social media posts shared during this period.

Figure 11: Introductory post for the social media campaign on Women's Day - March 2023

Figure 12: Social media posts for the campaign on Women's Day - March 2023

All posts containing the relevant information were gathered to create a blog post titled “[When did women first vote in elections in the FIERCE countries?](#)”. This blog post was then published on the project website.

Impact of the campaign

Using the Analytics tool provided by each platform, we can quantify the impact of the campaign. Specifically, during the period between March 8th and March 10th, 2023, our content was displayed to users approximately 1800 times (total impressions), eliciting 67 reactions such as likes and shares. As shown from the following table, the most effective social media platform for FIERCE is X (Twitter).

Social Medium	Impressions	Reactions
LinkedIn	361	16
Facebook	320	15
X (Twitter)	1079	36
Total	1760	67

Table 5: Social media metrics featuring the impact of the social media campaign on Women's Day - March 2023

2.3.2. Campaign on the International Day for the Elimination of Violence Against Women

Following a similar approach, another social media campaign was conducted in November 2023, on the occasion of the International Day for the Elimination of Violence Against Women. Given that Gender-Based Violence (GBV) is one of the five primary research topics of our project, this occasion provided an excellent opportunity not only to raise awareness about the issue but also to offer practical support and advice for victims of GBV in each project country. Additionally, a joint campaign on our social media channels occurred jointly with our sister projects (for more info on the joint campaign see section 2.15)

Like the previous campaign, the T6.1 leader informed partners about the concept, and then, they provided their respective national contact points and/or national shelters for abused women and marginalized groups. Tailor-made posters for each project country, along with a “teaser” poster for social media announcements, were created by the T6.1 leader for this occasion. The following figures demonstrate some of the social media posts shared during this period.

Figure 13: Introductory post for the social media campaign for the International Day for the Elimination of Violence Against Women - November 2023

FIERCE
298 followers
2mo · 🌐

🌟 FIERCE countries against Gender-Based Violence - DENMARK

We're thrilled to launch our campaign against **#GenderBasedViolence!** 🟢
Throughout this week, we'll be sharing vital resources for all the 8 project countries.

- ♦ For Denmark, one crucial resource is the national hotline of the organization **Lev Uden Vold** (Live without Violence).
🔗 Link: <https://lnkd.in/d5AN9wdn>
- ♦ Explore more valuable information through **KVINFO**, a national knowledge center for gender and equality.
🔗 Link: <https://lnkd.in/d9SqG3-E>

Join us in raising awareness and standing against Gender-Based Violence! 🙌
#EndGBV #GBVAwareness

📺 Stay tuned for more resources against **#GBV** from the **#FIERCEprojectEU** countries

💛 Our **#FIERCEprojectEU** team:
ViLabs | Institut for Politik & Samfund, Aalborg Universitet | Scuola Normale Superiore | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Smart Venice | European Alternatives | University of Gdansk | Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) | Peace Institute, Institute for Contemporary Social and Political Studies | Koç University | University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Arts

#WeAreFIERCE #HorizonEurope #Democracy #Inclusion #Feminism

European Research Executive Agency (REA)

 FIERCE
Forcible Interventions
enabling Outcomes in Europe

#FIERCEprojectEU
#EndGBV

Denmark

🕒 1888

🌐 www.levudenvold.dk
www.kvinfo.dk

📘 Lev Uden Vold (Live without Violence) operates the national hotline for victims, victims or perpetrators of violence and their relatives, as well as professionals. KVINFO is a national knowledge center for gender and equality.

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Figure 14: Social media posts for the campaign on the International Day for the Elimination of Violence Against Women - November 2023

From November 20th to November 24th, 2023, the 8 informative posters (one for each of our 8 countries) were shared across our social media channels and subsequently used to create a blog post featured on the project website, titled "[FIERCE Countries Against Gender-Based Violence](#)".

Impact of the campaign

The quantitative metrics extracted from the Analytics tool of each platform indicate the extent to which the messages of the campaign reached our audience. From November 18th, when the “teaser” post went live, to November 24th, when the last post was published, our content was displayed on our social media platforms nearly 2,000 times (total impressions). As illustrated in the table below, X (Twitter) and LinkedIn emerge as the most impactful channels for our project, both in terms of impressions and reactions

Social Medium	Impressions	Reactions
LinkedIn	747	20
Facebook	222	11
X (Twitter)	897	17
Instagram	51	16
Total	1917	64

Table 6: Social media metrics featuring the impact of the social media campaign on the International Day for the Elimination of Violence Against Women - November 2023

2.4. Dissemination Materials for FIERCE events

Apart from the project’s promotional materials that were available from the early beginning of the project, tailor-made dissemination materials have been created for various project needs.

- **Invitations to the National Labs**

In project month M8 (April 2023), poster invitations were prepared to facilitate the invitation of various target actors to the 1st round of the National Labs held in each project country. In collaboration with SV, the WP4 leader, tailored invitations were created to address four different stakeholder groups: feminist activists, policymakers, academics and scholars, and political actors. Additionally, a generic invitation including all target groups was provided to partners, offering them the flexibility to choose between a generic or tailored invitation to send to candidate participants of the labs.

The invitations were circulated to partners in English, with the option for translation into their respective national languages. As these invitations were strategically targeted to specific individuals, they were not promoted on our online channels but stored in the project’s repository for future use in subsequent rounds of national labs.

Screenshots of the invitations in both English and national languages are provided in the following figures.

OPEN CALL

OPEN CALL

OPEN CALL

What is FIERCE?

The EU-funded **FIERCE** project, led by a team of feminist 'academic activists' and researchers, aims to:

- Understand **feminist and opposing actors**, activities, and discourses, and their impact on institutions and policies.
- Study democratic practices of feminist movements and organizations, and develop joint initiatives to **strengthen democracy in Europe**.
- Support international and intersectional **alliances** within feminist movements and cross-movements, and liaise with civil society and political decision-makers.

To this aim, we will be conducting in the upcoming 2 years concrete actions such as:

- the FIERCE Labs,
- a Transnational Feminist Network,
- co-funded Feminist Democratic Innovations,
- and a Feminist Summer School.

Why should you join?

Are you a feminist activist?

- **Exchange** with other movements, expanding cross-movements alliances.
- Establish **international alliances** with other actors through the participation in the transnational Lab and network.
- Access the **project's research results** about anti-gender movements.
- **Participate** in other activities, such as the open call for the co-funding **FIERCE feminist actions**, and the **Feminist Summer School**.

Are you a political actor?

- Expand **political alliances** with feminist movements toward political agenda setting or implementation.
- Increase **accountability** towards feminist civil society.
- Increase **legitimacy** regarding gender/feminist/intersectional issues.

Are you involved in policymaking?

- Receive **first-hand inputs** from feminist movements so as to integrate or take them into account in **public policy implementation**.
- Enhance gender mainstreaming and **increase intersectoral alignment/synergies** in your technical work.

Are you an academic or a scholar?

- Gain increased **know-how** and **scientific knowledge** on the topics at stake.
- **Access FIERCE** research results.
- Establish **connections and networking**.

What are the FIERCE Labs?

Dialogue and exchange spaces for pressing feminist issues. Feminist actors and allies will co-create initiatives like campaigns, position papers, and policy statements.

The Labs in practice:

8 country Labs, mainly engaging feminist movements, to launch in:

A transnational forum will foster networking and alliances.

Each Lab having **20 people** meeting in-person for 3 full-day meetings over one year starting from June 2023.

Online exchange/working sessions in between meetings.

Final output will be based on **context, strategy, and creativity shared**.

Reimbursement fees (up to 70%) for travel and accommodation expenses provided.

Funded by the European Union

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.

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Figure 15: General invitation for the National Labs - English

FIERCE Fundacja Zatoka
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CZYM JEST FIERCE?
FIERCE to międzynarodowy, finansowany przez UE projekt, prowadzony przez zespół osób zaangażowanych w działania feministyczne oraz badaczy i badaczki akademickich z krajów: Polski, Danii, Francji, Słowenii, Turcji, Włoch, Grecji, Hiszpanii.

FIERCE ma na celu:

- Poznanie feministycznych i antyfeministycznych podmiotów, organizacji, ruchów, ich działań oraz dyskursów, a także ich wpływu na krajowe i międzynarodowe instytucje i politykę.
- Poznanie demokratycznych praktyk ruchów i organizacji feministycznych oraz rozwijanie wspólnych inicjatyw na rzecz wzmocnienia demokracji w Europie.
- Wspieranie międzynarodowych i interseksyjnych porozumień w ramach ruchów feministycznych oraz społeczeństwa obywatelskiego, a także współpraca w tym celu z decydentami politycznymi.

Aby zrealizować te cele w ciągu najbliższych 2 lat będziemy podejmować konkretne działania, m.in.:

- warsztaty FIERCE z osobami aktywnymi działającymi w ramach ruchów feministycznych, tworzenie Transnarodowej Sieci Feministycznej,
- wspieranie feministycznych innowacji demokratycznych, organizacja Feministycznej Szkoły Letniej.

OPEN CALL OPEN CALL OPEN CALL

CZYM SĄ WARSZTATY FIERCE?
Przeznaczone dla dialogu i wymiany w zakresie najważniejszych kwestii feministycznych. Podczas warsztatów osoby feministyczne oraz ich sojusznicy i sojuszniczki będą współtworzyć inicjatywy takie jak kampanie, dokumenty określające stanowiska i oświadczenia polityczne.

Ostateczny rezultat warsztatów będzie oparty na kontekście, strategii i kreatywności osób uczestniczących. Warsztaty będą organizowane niezależnie w 8 krajach.

a rezultaty uzyskane w ramach tych warsztatów będą następnie rozwijane na transnarodowym forum, złożonym z przedstawicielek i przedstawicieli krajowych warsztatów, które dodatkowo będzie sprzyjać tworzeniu sieci i porozumień międzynarodowych.

Przebieg warsztatów: Każdy warsztat/Laboratorium będzie liczył 20 osób, które spotkają się osobistnie na trzechspotkaniach organizowanych w ciągu roku. Pierwsze spotkanie odbędzie się 17 czerwca 2023 r. w Warszawie. Miejsce: AKUMULATOR-PRZESTRZEŃ SĄSIEDZKA, ul. Reymowskiego 32, w godz. 9.00-16.00

Organizatorzy mają środki na koszty podróży i zakwaterowania oraz przymy węgierski lunch i przekąski podczas spotkania.

Funded by the European Union

Figure 16: Tailored invitation for the Polish National Lab

FIERCE
www.fierce-project.eu
info@fierce-project.eu

Cos'è FIERCE?
Il progetto dell'UE FIERCE è promosso da un gruppo di «attivistici accademici» e ricercatrici/ori che, con un approccio di ricerca azione partecipativa, mirano a:

- Fornire una comprensione degli attori femministi e dei loro oppositori anti-gender, a livello di discorsi e mobilitazioni, così come l'impatto che questi hanno avuto sulle istituzioni e le politiche durante.
- Studiare le pratiche democratiche dei movimenti e organizzazioni femministe e sviluppare iniziative congiunte che possano contribuire al rafforzamento della democrazia in Europa.
- Sostenere alleanze internazionali e intersezionali tra i movimenti femministi, altri movimenti sociali, la società civile e i decisori politici.

A tal fine, nei prossimi due anni, saranno promosse azioni concrete, quali:

- un bando per co-finanziare iniziative democratiche femministe,
- I FIERCE labs nazionali e transnazionali, una rete transnazionale femminista,
- e una summer school femminista.

Tema del Lab italiano:
Educare alle differenze - Manuale di autodifesa per insegnanti.

29 giugno 2023
Dalle 10:00 alle 17:00

Il Giardino dei Ciliegi
(Via dell'Agnolo, 5, 50018 Firenze FI)

Cosa sono i FIERCE labs?
Spazi di dialogo e scambio sulle questioni più urgenti delle agende politiche femministe. Diversi attori femministi si incontreranno e decideranno i temi specifici da affrontare, co-creando azioni orientate a contribuire alle lotte femministe intersezionali, sviluppando iniziative concrete quali campagne, mobilitazioni, position papers, etc.

I labs in pratica:
Otto labs nazionali che coinvolgeranno principalmente attivisti femministi.

Un lab transnazionale che promuoverà networking e alleanze tra partecipanti dei labs nazionali e attori femministi a livello europeo.

Ogni lab nazionale coinvolgerà circa 20 persone in tre incontri in presenza di un'intera giornata, che si svolgeranno nell'arco di un anno a partire da giugno 2023.

Tra gli incontri in presenza sono previste sessioni di scambio/lavoro online.

Il risultato finale del lab (iniziativa concreta sviluppata) cambierà secondo il contesto, la strategia concordata tra i/le partecipanti e la creatività del gruppo.

Sono disponibili fondi per coprire fino al 70% delle spese di viaggio e alloggio dei partecipanti.

Per più informazioni scrivere a: oriana.salomon@smarvenice.org

Funded by the European Union

Figure 17: Tailored invitation for the Italian National Lab

- **Presentation booklet for the 1st Transnational Lab**

To support the communication needs of the [1st Transnational Lab](#) held in September 2023 (M12), the T6.1 leader, with the support of the WP4 leader (SV), prepared a presentation booklet of the participants, aiming to reflect our diverse and talented community accurately.

The concept was to create an internal-use booklet showcasing all individuals involved in the 1st Transnational Lab meeting. The material was circulated to the participants, including members of the FIERCE team, participants from the National Labs, Advisory Board members, and participants from other EU organizations, in advance of the meeting. This allowed everyone to introduce themselves before the meeting took place.

To facilitate the implementation and coordination of this initiative, given the large number of participants, the T6.1 leader created an online form. Participants were asked to fill out their information, either all or part of, if they preferred not to share certain data. The majority of participants shared all requested information, including their full name, a short bio, the name and logo of the organization they represent, a contact email, and a photo.

The data were promptly collected by ViLabs and deleted after the completion of the material. The booklet was organized into categories of participants. After a short welcome message, the Advisory Board members, event facilitators, FIERCE partners, participants from the National Labs, and participants from EU organizations were presented in alphabetical order based on their surname. The document concluded with a last page featuring the project's contact points. Relevant screenshots are being displayed below.

Figure 18: Screenshots from the Presentation Booklet - 1st Transnational Lab

- **Poster for the first online roundtable discussion**

To support the communication needs of the first online [roundtable](#) discussion organized as part of WP4 activities, the following poster was created in two versions: horizontal and vertical, to best suit various online platforms that were used for the promotion.

FIERCE
Feminist movements
revitalizing Democracy in Europe.

Feminist Agendas in the 2024 EP?
Reaching out to the candidates

Roundtable Discussion

WHEN? - January the 9th, 2024 | 14:00-16:00 CET

WHERE? - online (ZOOM) | [link to connect](#)

[REGISTER](#)

SPEAKERS

KEY-NOTE

Neil Datta European Parliamentary Forum for Sexual and Reproductive Rights Executive Director	Xenia Kellner Young Feminist Europe Co-founder: Advocacy & Policy Coordinator	Sonja Lokar Women's Lobby of Slovenia President	Gea Meijers WIDE+ Coordinator

TOPICS OF THE ROUNDTABLE:

1. Lessons learned from previous experiences in developing campaigns at the European level.
2. Effectively communicating European feminist agendas to new candidates for the EP 2024 elections.
3. Needs of the EP to develop an agenda supporting feminism and gender equality.

Funded by the European Union

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Figure 19: Vertical poster for the first online roundtable discussion

With the support of the WP4 leader, key details of the keynote speakers, including their photos, as well as discussion topics and other relevant information, were provided to the T6.1 leader to create the different promotional materials. These posters were featured on the project website in a dedicated news item, on our social media platforms, and distributed to consortium partners for further dissemination.

As part of the communication strategy for promoting the event, each speaker was introduced individually on social media.

Figure 20: Social media posts for the speakers of the first online roundtable discussion

Further details about each stage of the promotion will be analyzed in sub-chapter 2.12, “Events Organized by FIERCE”.

2.5. Promotional Materials in partners’ languages

The FIERCE promotional materials were translated into the languages of the 8 partners in January 2024 (M17), fulfilling the relevant KPI. The translated brochures and posters can be found on the “[Communication Kit](#)” subpage of the project website.

Figure 21: Translated posters featured in the FIERCE website

Figure 22: Translated brochures featured in the FIERCE website

2.6. FIERCE Newsletter

There have been four [newsletters](#) published by the FIERCE project so far. Three of them were dedicated to informing our subscribed audience about the project's progress and achievements, while one was specifically created as part of our communication strategy to promote the 1st FIERCE online roundtable.

All newsletters can be found on the project website under the respective subpage "[Newsletter](#)".

Figure 23: FIERCE "Newsletter" webpage

The following table presents an overview of the publication dates and topics covered in each newsletter.

Newsletter No	Publication Date	Topic
1st Newsletter	February 2023 (M6)	Introduction to our audience informing them about the project, its scope and next planned actions.
2nd Newsletter	October 2023 (M13)	Activities that happened during the first year of the project with an emphasis on the successful completion of the first co-creation cycle.
3rd Newsletter	December 2023 (M16)	Special newsletter issue announcing the 1st FIERCE online roundtable discussion and inviting subscribers to join.
4th Newsletter	February 2024 (M18)	Activities that happened during the past year of the project with an emphasis on the successful completion of the second co-creation cycle.

Table 7: Publication Date and Topic of the FIERCE Newsletters

Newsletter subscribers – Community of stakeholders

According to data extracted from Mailchimp, the platform used for creating FIERCE newsletters, there are currently 138 subscribers while the current report is being conducted. Our subscription form requires subscribers to identify themselves based on their background and activity, such as Other EU networks, Civil society, policymakers, feminist activists, and researchers. Therefore, the following data can be extracted and are presented in the diagram below.

Figure 24: Statistics for the newsletter subscribers

To increase the number of subscribers, “teaser” social media posts announcing an upcoming newsletter are posted a few days before its publication. The following figures represent graphics prepared for posting in social media channels before and after the newsletter publication.

Figure 25: Tailored visual graphics for promoting the FIERCE newsletter

2.7. Press Releases

There are currently four [press releases](#) available on the FIERCE website. Regarding the first press release, VIL prepared it as a template text for partners to fill in their respective information and disseminate it in their networks, either in English or in their respective languages.

All newsletters are displayed on the project website in chronological order.

Press Release

On this page, you can access the press release documents of the project. FIERCE disseminates important aspects of its progression via press releases published either on European or national media, in English or in national languages.

FIERCE | Invitation to the 1st FIERCE Online Roundtable Discussion

"Feminist agendas in the 2024 European Parliament? Reaching out to the candidates"

December 13, 2023

[READ THE PRESS RELEASE](#)

Europa Wire | The Feminist Movements Revitalizing Democracy in Europe (FIERCE) project kicks-off!

September 7, 2022

[DOWNLOAD THE PRESS RELEASE](#) | [READ THE PRESS RELEASE](#)

VIL Press release | ViLabs goes FIERCE!

August 1, 2022

[READ THE PRESS RELEASE](#)

AAU Press release | New project – Feminist Movements Revitalising Democracy in Europe

April 1, 2022

Figure 26: FIERCE "Press Release" webpage

2.8. Publications

Two conference papers have been published during this reporting period, produced by our partners from UL. All publications are available and openly accessible at the project website under the “[Publications](#)” subpage, at the ZENODO Community and at the [Genport](#). The following table presents an overview of the information regarding these publications.

Title	Partner	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent	Peer-review	Open access	Link	PID of deposited publication
Teorija spola kot prevladujoč okvir javne razprave o spolu in spolnosti: diskurzivna dediščina antigenderskega gibanja (Gender theory as a dominant framework for public debate on gender and sexuality: the discursive legacy of the anti-gender movement)	UL	Rok Smrdelj, Roman Kuhar, Monika Kalin Golob	Dolgoživa družba: posledice in izzivi: Slovensko sociološko srečanje (conference abstracts)	Yes	Yes	https://www.sociolosko-drustvo.si/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/SSD-ZBORNIK-povzetkov-A5-23-WEB-1.pdf	ISBN 978-961-94302-9-3
Anti-gender discursive “legacy”: framing gender debate by opposing “gender theory”	UL	Rok Smrdelj, Roman Kuhar, Monika Kalin Golob	Making a difference: the hope and promise of sexuality studies : book of abstracts : midterm conference of European Sociological Association Sexuality Research Network	yes	yes	https://esarn23.files.wordpress.com/2023/09/abstract_book_esarn23-1.pdf	

Table 8: Publications overview M7-M18

2.9. Blogs

Overachieving our target KPI for 1 blog per month, we currently count 30 blogs in the FIERCE website under the subpage “Blogs”.

Figure 27: FIERCE "Blogs" webpage

In collaboration with our project partners, three blog series were created in the project period so far. The first one, titled “Meet the FIERCE Team”, was an introductory one, in which all partners presented the organizations they represent, explained their roles in the project, and expressed their expectations for the project’s results and impact.

The second blog series, titled “Why is FIERCE Relevant to...?” was created by the eight project national cases, with them answering the question of why FIERCE is relevant to their countries. The third series, titled “Wins of Feminism”, was created by partners, providing details on the wins of the feminist movement in their respective countries during the period 2010-2021, based on D2.1 were shared by our partners.

Finally, there are two more blogs, which were created from the content partners provided during the social media campaigns on International Women’s Day (March 2023) and the International Day for the Elimination of Violence Against Women (November 2023). Our Danish partners also provided one more blog on Feminism in Denmark.

Our blogs have been promoted on our social media channels, inviting our audience to view and engage with them. For that reason, tailored visual materials were created to accompany the social media posts and “catch the eye” of the reader, making it more attractive for them to engage with our content.

Figure 28: Digital banners used in the social media promotion of the blogs

2.10. Podcasts

For the podcasts, our target KPI is to produce at least 8 podcast episodes. During the reporting period, one podcast was produced by UL, our Slovenian partners, in their national language. It was shared on the platform of the Slovenian Sociological Association and already had 190 downloads in the first few days after publishing, with the number increasing. The podcast is available in the FIERCE website under the subpage “[Podcasts](#)”.

FIERCE set up its official account on Spotify, named “FIERCE Dialogues,” in February 2024 (M18). To facilitate the implementation process of the podcasts, detailed guidelines have been prepared by the T6.1 leader to help partners identify the podcast topics, organize the structure, and be prepared for the technicalities.

The T6.1 leader has also created an intro and outro, created a test podcast, and designed a visual graphic to accompany the podcasts in their publications. It has also been agreed among partners that VIL (T6.1 leader) will be participating in the recording of the podcast discussions to ensure smooth progress. Podcasts will be available on spotify as an audio but also a video of the episode will be uploaded on the project youtube channel to reach also audience who might encounter audio disabilities. In the upcoming period it is foreseen to record and publish more podcast episodes.

Figure 29: Digital banner created for the podcasts

2.11. Videos

For the videos, our target KPI is to produce at least 3 videos during the lifecycle of the project. Our first [video](#), an introductory and promotional video about FIERCE created by VIL and shared with partners for feedback. Upon agreement by the partners the video was published on our YouTube channel. It was further promoted in other channels.

Additionally, our UCM partners prepared a [short video](#) during their second National Lab. After receiving the consensus of the participants involved, it was also published on our YouTube channel.

2.12. Events organized by FIERCE

During this reporting period, there are two external open and outreach events that FIERCE organized.

[FIERCE at the gender equality festival “Talk Town” \(LINK\)](#)

Date: 24 November 2023 (M15) | **Location:** Copenhagen, Denmark | **Partner:** AAU

On November 24th, the FIERCE project contributed to organizing a panel discussion with the title “Sexism from a minority perspective” at the gender equality festival “Talk Town” in Copenhagen, Denmark.

The panel discussion was organized by a network of organizations that share a critical focus on how sexism can have an intersectional character and affect minorities in other ways than the majority population. Besides the FIERCE project, organizations such as Everyday Sexism Project Denmark, Disabled People’s Organizations Denmark, Sabaah, and Tegnbuen participated in this network.

Figure 30: Photos from the gender equality festival “Talk Town” in Copenhagen – November 2023

[1st FIERCE Online Roundtable Discussion \(LINK\)](#)

Date: 09 January 2024 (M17) | **Location:** Online | **Partner:** SV

In the context of WP4 activities, an online roundtable discussion titled “Feminist agendas in the 2024 EP? Reaching out to the candidates” took place in January 2024. The roundtable was organised as part of the co-creation process of the FIERCE Transnational Lab, where a campaign for the 2024 European Parliament (EP) elections will be designed and implemented.

In collaboration with SV, our communication strategy for the event consisted of the following actions:

- A dedicated Press Release, containing information provided by SV to the T6.1 leader, was published on the project website in December 2023 (M16). It was also circulated via email to consortium partners, National and Transnational Lab participants for further promotion.
- A dedicated newsletter for the event was created by the T6.1 leader to raise awareness among the FIERCE newsletter subscribers.
- Two posters were created and shared on the project's social media channels.
- Social media features were utilized to create “Events” where participants could confirm their attendance, allowing social media channels to send them reminders before the meeting.
- The registration link was shared in multiple social media posts relevant to the event.
- A social media presentation campaign of the speakers occurred a few days before the event, sharing information about their backgrounds.

It's important to note that all social media posts included mentions (tags) of the participants and the organizations they represented to facilitate their engagement and resharing. Additionally, all project partners were also mentioned (tagged) in these social media posts, as well as the official accounts of the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Finally, just before the online roundtable began, a final social media post was made with a call-to-action for people to join.

Figure 31: Social media post promoting the online roundtable discussion

2.13. FIERCE in ECPR conference

One major external event in which our partners participated is the European Consortium for Political Research (ECPR) conference 2023 with a panel titled “Doing Feminism in Times of Global Anti-Gender Mobilizations”.

At the ECPR Conference 2023, held from September 4th to 8th (M13), our FIERCE partners presented an array of papers focusing on the challenges and evolutions of feminist movements and anti-gender actors in various political climates. The research primarily focuses on the current political climates of Greece, Denmark, Turkey, Poland, Slovenia, France, and Italy.

Figure 32: Photos from partners presentation at the ECPR conference 2023

For more information on conferences, workshops, and external events where partners disseminated preliminary findings of the research conducted, please refer to section 2.16.

2.14. Interviews

An interview took place online in December 2023 involving our UL partners and was in the context of the podcast “Antifeminismus (1/3): Antifeministische Narrative – ein Überblick, series: Our voices, our choices, Heinrich Böll Stiftung” about the reasons for anti-gender movement in Europe and beyond. The key points that were shared from our partners’ side were partly based on the results from FIERCE.

2.15. Synergies with FIERCE’s sister projects

After establishing communication with representatives from our “sister” projects, meaning the projects that received funding under the same Call as FIERCE, a dedicated page on our website was created for this purpose. These EU funded projects include CCINDLE, PushBackLash, UNTWIST, and RESIST. On the “[Clustering](#)” webpage, our sister projects were featured along with a short description and their online channels.

The online promotion of the sister projects also includes the cross-promotion of our activities on social media. The following figures demonstrate cross-promotion in our LinkedIn accounts between FIERCE and the CCINDLE project.

Figure 33: Reshare of CCINDLE content from the FIERCE account

Figure 34: Reshare of FIERCE content from the CCINDLE account

A joint campaign on our social media channels occurred on the occasion of the International Day for the Elimination of Violence Against Women on November 25th, 2023 (M15). Representatives from the sister projects were informed about our campaign proposal in October 2023 (M14), and the PushBackLash project responded positively.

The concept shared was that each project would use the graphic template created by FIERCE on their social media channels. This graphic would include a concise statement against Gender-Based Violence.

To maximize the impact of this action, we suggested incorporating an informative resource (publication, article, book, statistics, research findings, etc.) into the copy of the social media post that aligns with the theme of Gender-Based Violence.

The [social media posts](#) shared by FIERCE and the PushBackLash project in November 2023 are presented in the following figures.

The banner features the FIERCE logo (Feminist movements revitalizing Democracy in Europe) and the PUSH*BACK*LASH logo. The main text reads: "Challenging Gender-Based Violence Norms: Together We Can! At FIERCE, we stand united against Gender-Based Violence. Every voice matters, and together, we strive to create a world where respect, equality, and justice prevail. As part of our ongoing efforts, our comparative analysis spans 8 EU countries, and specifically focuses on 5 critical areas, including the urgent matter of Gender-Based Violence." Below this is the text "The FIERCE project". At the bottom left is the European Union logo with the text "Funded by the European Union". At the bottom right is a disclaimer: "Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them." The background is a red and yellow diagonal split with a photo of raised fists.

Figure 35: Digital banner shared by FIERCE

The banner features the FIERCE logo and the PUSH*BACK*LASH logo. The main text reads: "Challenging Gender-Based Violence Norms: Together We Can!" followed by a bulleted list:

- 1 in 3 women in the EU has experienced physical or sexual violence.
- The Istanbul Convention holds states accountable if they do not sufficiently address violence against women.
- Not every EU member state has ratified this Convention.
- Andrea Krizsán and Conny Roggeband explain why in "Politicizing Gender and Democracy in the Context of the Istanbul Convention."

Below this is the text "The Push*Back*Lash project". At the bottom left is the European Union logo with the text "Funded by the European Union". At the bottom right is a disclaimer: "Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them." The background is a red and yellow diagonal split with a photo of raised fists.

Figure 36: Digital banner shared by PushBackLash

Newsletters can serve as a platform for cross-promotion between “sister” projects. In the [second](#) issue of our newsletter, we introduced a special section dedicated to showcasing the work of our “sister” projects. In each subsequent newsletter, FIERCE will highlight aspects of our Sisters' work.

In the second issue, we featured a blog from the CCINDLE project.

Keeping up with our Sisters!

CCINDLE project

RESIST project

PUSHBACKLASH project

UNTWIST project

At FIERCE, we believe in the power of **collaboration!**

We have created a dedicated page on our website showcasing our sister projects with which we share a common vision of a more inclusive democracy in Europe and opened up communication channels with the overall aim of increasing our projects' impact through collaborative activities.

Expore our page!

In each newsletter issue, we are going to showcase parts of the work of our Sisters! We kick off this initiative with an interesting **blog post** from the **CCINDLE** project, titled "**Democracy and feminist politics: a crucial relationship**".

In their insightful blog post, the CCINDLE project highlights how feminist politics democratizes the state, empowers marginalized voices, and promotes gender equality. Using Barcelona as a case study, they illustrate how feminist institutional politics can transform municipal institutions and promote intersectional equality.

Read the full article here!

Figure 37: Part of the 2nd FIERCE newsletter promoting CCINDLE project

In the following period and as projects start to produce results ready for open dissemination, more joint activities will take place, considering joint blogs and podcasts.

2.16. Partners' communication and dissemination activities

During this reporting period, our partners participated in various external events, contributing to the dissemination of FIERCE. To facilitate partners' access to information about upcoming events, a dedicated Excel file, created by the T6.1 leader and stored in the project repository, includes event details such as title, type, date, location, abstract deadline, relevant links, and contact information if available. The following figure is a screenshot of this file.

Title	Type	Date	Location	Abstract deadline	Participating partner(s)	Short description	Contact Info
ECPG conference	Conference	8-10 July 2024	Ghent university	7 December 2023		https://ecpr.eu/Events/AcademicProgramme/Programme?EventID=253https://www.tickettailor.com/events/lse/departmentofgenderstudies/1065394	
11th European Workshops in International Studies - The future yet to come: for a global politics of hope	Call for papers & Workshops	3-5 July 2024	Istanbul, Turkey	Call for workshops close on Nov 23 Decisions on successful workshops announced Dec 12 General call for papers close Feb 2		https://eisa-net.org/ewis-2024/	

Figure 38: Screenshot from the events list file

The following table provides a summary of partners' communication activities during this reporting period (M7-M18), as reported by the partners themselves. In addition to detailing the partner(s) involved in the communication and dissemination activities below, each activity is accompanied by a brief description, the project month the activity took place, and a relevant link to the activity (if available), which has been promoted either in the FIERCE channels or the partners' channels.

Partner	Communication & Dissemination Activity Description	Mx	Link (if applicable)
VIL	Participation in the final conference of SPEAR project. Participation at the sister project's section highlighting FIERCE	M7	https://fierce-project.eu/fierce-participates-at-spear-conference/
VIL	FIERCE presentation at the Greek national seminar for Cluster 2 "Culture, Creativity, and Inclusive Society" of Horizon Europe organized by the PRAXI/ITE Network, with the support of the General Secretariat for Research and Innovation and the European Commission,	M16	https://praxinetwork.gr/el/doclib/HorizonEurope/Cluster2/Info_Day_Cluster_2.mp4?fbclid=IwAR1ga6R9GepSYpinjLomdmUCcfsakI1Y3JB9sjVoOAoe5Tie5p8XlxtnY6I

VIL	Participation in the final event organized by RESISTIRE project (gender-related project). Participation at the sister project's section highlighting FIERCE.	M10	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7077273604014358529
AAU	Panel discussion with the title "Sexism from a minority perspective" at the gender equality festival Talk Town in Copenhagen, Denmark	M15	https://fierce-project.eu/fierce-at-the-gender-equality-festival-talk-town-in-copenhagen/
EA	Journal Article titled "Transnational Feminism and Its Foes", published in the Green European Journal	M16	https://www.greeneuropeanjournal.eu/transnational-feminism-and-its-foes/
MI	Webpage post on the MI's website about the second project meeting in national language	M9	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/na-danskem-o-potencialih-feministicnih-gibanj-za-krepitev-demokracicnih-praks/
UL, MI	Podcast discussion focusing on the issue of sexual and reproductive rights.	M10	https://fierce-project.eu/podcasts/
VIL	Participation in the conference of the genderaction+ project Participation at the sister project's section highlighting FIERCE	M18	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7165628978169274369
AAU, SNS, EA, UG, AUTH, MI, KU, UL, VIL	Paper presentation of initial results at the ECPR conference to an international research audience to review progress in research and explore possible future directions in the field.	M13	https://fierce-project.eu/fierce-will-participate-at-the-ecpr-conference-2023/
AAU	Presentation to the students at Institute for Politics and Society at Aalborg University	M15	N/A
AAU	Paper presentation for the first seminar in the Gender- and Intersectionality Netværk at Aalborg University (GINAAU).	M14	N/A

AAU	Paper presentation for a consent-based rape legislation in Denmark at the annual meeting of the Danish Political Science Association	M15	N/A
AAU	Presentation for high-school students, where AAU partners presented their research and preliminary findings of FIERCE to Danish high-school students	M14	N/A
AAU	Presentation to other scholars - who provided relevant feedback on particularly the co-creation labs - at the seminar "Democratic Imaginaries" organized as part of the 2-year project "Mobilizing for Democracy: People, Borders, and Imagination."	M10	https://fierce-project.eu/aalborg-university-partners-present-the-fierce-project-at-the-seminar-democratic-imaginaries/
AAU	Presentation at a workshop in the network "Masculinity, masculinist politics, and political extremism in the Nordic", mainly to get feedback on on-going work in the Danish team with WP1	M9	N/A
SNS	Presentation of preliminary findings of WP2 titled "The new wave of feminist movements in Europe" within the course on "Theories of democracy" at Scuola Normale Superiore.	M6	N/A
SNS	Presentation of preliminary findings of WP2 titled "Feminist movements and democracy" at the conference "Femminismi" at Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa	M7	N/A
SNS	Presentation of preliminary findings of WP2 titled "The new wave of feminist movements in Europe" at a seminar at the Centre on gender studies, University of Milan.	M14	N/A

SNS	Panel at SISP conference in Genoa titled "Feminist movements and democracy", where preliminary findings of WP2 were shared.	m13	https://www.sisp.it/convegno2023/?pagename=progman&pubblica=true&tto=true
SNS	Participation in a workshop in Geneva titled "Intersectionality and feminist movements in Italy" to prepare a special issue on intersectionality and feminism for the journal EJPG	M15	N/A
UCM	Presentation of preliminary findings at the conference "Anti-feminist backlash, manosphere and masculinity(ies)".	M6	N/A
UCM	Presentation of initial results to an international research audience to review progress in research and explore possible future directions in the field at the Panel on "Gender & the Far Right" of the 29th Council of European Studies Conference, University of Iceland, Reykiavik.	M10	N/A
UG	Meeting with contentious politics research cluster at Coventry University, where the Polish research team was invited to present initial outcomes of the project	M8	N/A
MI	Paper presentation titled "Feminist activism against democracy back-lash: experiences from post-socialist Slovenia" at the "European Politics, Equality and Democracy" conference.	M9	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/gostovanje-konferenca-helsinki/
MI	Paper presentation titled "Anti-gender Mobilization: Defending 'the Traditional' from a Post-sexual Imaginary in Central-Eastern Europe" at the "Anti-feminism and anti-gender politics in authoritarian regimes" conference.	M10	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/conference-on-anti-gender-in-authoritarian-regimes/

MI, UL	Paper presentation titled "Anti-gender Backlash in Central-Eastern Europe: Instrumentalizing the Crisis" at the "Europe's past, present and future: utopias and dystopias" conference.	M10	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/gender-and-the-far-right-at-the-conference-europes-past-present-and-future/
MI	Lecture titled "Re-nationalizing citizenship at the example of the anti-gender movement in Central-Eastern Europe" at the Inter-University Centre Dubrovnik, Divided Societies XXIV: Nationalism and Violence.	M9	N/A
MI	A webpage post with a short report from the roundtable "Feminism and reproductive rights" organized as a part of first national lab	M11	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/feminizem-in-reproduktivne-pravice/
MI	A webpage post about the project meeting and transnational lab in Madrid	M18	meeting-and-designing-a-feminist-campaign-for-the-upcoming-european-elections/
UL	Presentation of preliminary findings to an international research audience at the ESA RN23 Sexuality, 'Making a difference: the hope and promise of sexuality studies' conference in order to review research progress and propose potential future directions in the subject in focus.	M13	N/A
UL	Presentation of selected results at the feminist summer school "Feministička škola Žarene Papić", Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina.	M13	N/A
UL	Keynote speech based on Fierce results titled "Reponse to anti-gender mobilizations: "Resisting Gender Equality: Unmasking the Dynamics of Anti-Gender Opposition" at Gender Summit, Skopje, North Macedonia.	M12	N/A

UL	Participation in a panel discussion on the anti-gender movement at an event in Belgrade at the Institute for Philosophy and Social Theory and presentation of the research results on the study on the anti-gender movement.	M11	N/A
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Table 9: Partners dissemination activities M7-M18

3. Exploitation and Sustainability Plan

During D6.1 a preliminary identification of the project key exploitable results (KERs) and the respective goals based on partners type of organization was made. In particular, we have identified 6 KERs: 1. Conceptual Framework of feminism and antifeminism movement analysis; 2. Transnational feminist Network; 3. Policy Toolkit; 4. FIERCE's training material; 5. FIERCE's Lessons Learnt; 6. FIERCE pilot actions. At this stage there is no update on KERs.

The table below depicts in detail the exploitation activities and objectives defined during the previous draft of D6.1 and present the progress until M18. As it is evident from the table below, efforts were placing the past period to identify relevant donor that could support the continued work from feminist grassroots organizations and perform a desk research on identifying the main components of the transferability guidebook (this is a work in progress).

A/A	Exploitation activity and objective	Audience	When?	KPIs	Progress
1	Workshops: Organize exploitation workshop(s) to work with partners on their individual exploitation plans	All consortium partners	Between M15-M32	Define concrete exploitation goals for each partner	Exploitation workshops under preparation by VIL. At this stage the specific outcome of these workshops as envisioned
2	Analysis: dedicated analysis on piloted actions and benefits for the various stakeholder categories	Pilot partners, external stakeholders	Between M21-M31	Define concrete benefits of the pilot actions	Not applicable yet since the pilot actions are planned to be realised Autumn 2024
3	A replication guidebook: will be developed to support the adaptability to replication and access to finance.	Feminist organisations	Between M21-M36	Define steps for adaptability and replicability of the FIERCE actions	A preliminary list with donors feeding into this has been drafted. Please see table below.
4	Consultation workshops with key actors to validate FIERCE's exploitation potential	All consortium partners and external stakeholders	Between M21-M36	Explore stakeholders interests	Not applicable yet. This will be happening during 2025
5	Mapping of grants and funding opportunities from different donors (foundations, multilateral agencies) that could support continued work from feminist grassroots organizations	Feminist grassroots organizations	Between M15-M36	Explore grants and funding opportunities	A preliminary list has been drafted. Please see table below.

Table 10 Exploitation activities and objectives – update

With an overall aim to draft the replication and transferability guidebook, as a first step, a preliminary list of donors supporting relevant entities such as civil society organizations, feminist organizations, etc across EU has been made. This donor's list include entities in particular that could support the continued work from feminist grassroots organizations. The list is draft and will be completed on M36 and included in D6.3. The list includes 15 entities in 11 EU countries and at EU level.

Country	Donor's name	website link	Type of donor (foundation /multilateral agency)	Type of funded entities (civil society organizations, feminist organizations, other)	Have they provided fundings during the last year? + add any relevant link
Denmark	The Danish Youth Council	DUF - Danish Youth Council	Umbrella organization	Broadly NGOs in Denmark and therefore also many of the feminist organizations	They distribute around 5-6 mio. euro per year. Here is one of their official reports on their economy (in Danish though): https://duf.dk/fileadmin/user_upload/Editor/documents/Om_DUF/Delegeretmoede/2021/12_11_12_regnskab.pdf
Denmark	Fundamental Rights Initiative (FRi) - collaboration between Global Focus and Nyt Europa	Globalt Fokus - The FRi grant - Fundamental Rights Initiative	NGOs (but co-founded by the EU)	NGOs (particularly those who focus on migration and LGBTQ+ rights - e.g. LGBT+ Denmark, Danish Refugee Council Youth) - also a clearly feminist one: An activist group called Men against patriarchy	ca. 1,5 mio. euro over the last couple of years
		https://femfund.pl/ Fundusz Feministyczny	grassroots fund	Small grants available for feminist projects and organizations (also informal) with very easy reporting	Several thousands of Euro's in the last year
		Fundacja Batorego	Foundation	Polish Soros partner, numerous calls for grants, also for feminist projects and initiatives, but subjected to peer review	few hundred thousand Euros per year

		https://www.batory.org.pl/			
EU level	WAVE - WOMEN AGAINST VIOLENCE EUROPE	https://wave-network.org/	European feminist organisation	Feminist civil society organisations (CSOs) which are part of their network. They launch yearly regranting activities among their members from the funds they receive from European Commission, European Education and Culture Executive Agency, under the CERV Programme.	2024 call for regranting activities: https://wave-network.org/wave-regranting/#call-for-proposals-2024
EU level	ILGA Europe	https://www.ilga-europe.org/ab-out-us/	European feminist organisation	European LGBTI organisations. In the 2024 call, they will fund a maximum of 12 organisations for projects that will last 12 months. Available budget of 25,000 euros per project	call for 2024 project proposals on racialized LGBTI communities: https://www.ilga-europe.org/news/no-one-left-behind-racialised-lgbti-communities/
France	The Support Fund for Feminist Organizations (FSOF)	https://www.aafd.fr/en/support-fund-feminist-organizations	Public/National Fund	Feminist Organizations, local civil society organizations working to promote gender equality and the rights of women and girls	€120 million over three years (2020, 2021, 2022 and 2023) to fund the activities of feminist movements around the world. No call for 2024.
Bulgaria	Bulgarian Fund for Women (BFW)	https://bgfundforwomen.org/en/	National feminist fund	Bulgarian Fund for Women is the only indigenous donor in Bulgaria that raises funds and gives grants to local NGOs working to advance women's and girls' rights, eliminate gender stereotypes, gender-based violence and discrimination, achieve gender equality in all spheres of life and make a social change.	BFW will distribute over € 1 million to 25 Civil Society Organizations in 2024 https://bgfundforwomen.org/en/2024/01/18/bfw-will-distribute-over-e-1-million-to-25-civil-society-organizations/

Spain	Calala Fondo de Mujeres	https://calala.org/	The only women's fund present in Spain. Part of 'Prospera', a network of more than 40 women's funds around the world.	Groups, networks and organizations of women and feminists who organise themselves in Spain and Central America to defend human rights and social justice, promoting real changes in their lives and in their communities. Organisations and groups that play a key role in advancing women's rights	Their last call for 2024 here: https://calala.org/abrimos-tercera-convocatoria-de-fondo-dalia/
Croatia	Ecumenical Women's Initiative	https://eiz.hr/en/mission/	Croatian non-profit organisation and women's fund	Women-led organisations and women theologians in Croatia and in Bosnia & Herzegovina, Kosovo, North Macedonia, Montenegro and Serbia for creative and innovative approaches to address issues which impact on their lives and those of their communities	Their last call for 2024 here: https://eiz.hr/en/grant/organisational-support-grants/
Germany	Filia.die frauenstiftung	https://www.filia-frauenstiftung.de/en/	German Foundation	Supports projects by and for women, girls and LGBTIQ+ that aim to bring about structural change – in Central and Eastern Europe, in the Global South and in Germany. Supports grassroots groups and networks that stand up for women's rights and want to encourage structural changes. Supports rojects and initiatives that work for freedom from violence, demand social participation and strengthen democratic structures.	There are currently no open call for proposals in 2024. But filia has so far enabled over 340 self-determined activities and projects of women, girls and LGBTIQ+ in 40 countries in different parts of the world (as of 2020). Approximately 80 per cent of the funds flow to projects worldwide.

France	Mediterranean Women's Fund	https://www.medwomensfund.org/	Multilateral Foundation	Women's movements in all of the countries of the Mediterranean region that demonstrate a strong commitment to equal rights for women and men and to human rights principles Associations or groups led by women: the majority of the top management must be women.	There are currently no open call for proposals in 2024. But their budget in 2023 was: 2.168.316 euros https://www.medwomensfund.org/docs/ffmed-lettre-appel-dons-2023.pdf
Serbia	Reconstruction Women's Fund	https://www.rwfund.org/eng/	Local women's foundation in Serbia Multilateral agency	Support autonomy of women's groups, whose programs affect the public and lead to strategic changes. Stimulate communication and exchange of women's activist, academic, artistic and pacifist experience and knowledge	Through their programme "Special Focus" https://www.rwfund.org/2024/01/25/konkurs-specijalni-fokus-novi-rok-je-16-februar/#more-17424
Ukrania	Ukrainian Women's Fund	https://uwf.org.ua/en/	Foundation	Support women's/feminist organizations, make for their participation in the development of a powerful, effective and mass women's/feminist movement capable of protecting women's rights and promoting gender equality in all areas. Activists and representatives of women's/feminist organizations	Open call for travel grants opportunity for activists and representatives of women's/feminist organizations as part of the Women's Voice and Leadership - Ukraine Project https://uwf.org.ua/en/travel-grants-for-activists-and-representatives-of-womens-feminist-organizations/
Armenia	Women's Fund Armenia	https://womenfundarmenia.org/	Local grant-making organization	supports women and girls in Armenia through capacity building, providing financial support and development of feminist movement	https://womenfundarmenia.org/call-for-cross-regional-cooperation-projects/

Georgia	Women's Fund in Georgia	https://www.womenfundgeorgia.org/en/WhatWeDo/Grantmaking/3677	Local funding organization dedicated to sustaining the women's rights' movement in Georgia	Awards grants to women organizations, initiative groups or individuals, that work on the improvement of women's lives	https://www.womenfundgeorgia.org/en/WhatWeDo/Grantmaking/3677
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Table 11 Donors' list

4. Conclusion and next steps

The present report has been conducted in order to provide a comprehensive overview of FIERCE's Consortium's effort to disseminate and communicate the project to the target audiences. The reported period includes M7 until M18. The documented activities have been clustered in accordance with the goal setting and the proposed actions elaborated in *D6.1*. This way, the current deliverable demonstrates continuity and provides the necessary evidence to the planning of the future actions of the project's dissemination and communication.

Overall, the project based its dissemination on concrete actions that feed into each other. First of all, the visual identity was created for online and on-site needs (for more information see *D6.1*). Drawing from a distinctive logo, digital and tangible materials were prepared, and the project's online channels were set up. Due to the co-creation activities foreseen during the project's implementation, the online channels of FIERCE are going to play an even more essential role in the overall dissemination efforts of the project. Taking all into account, attention will be paid to promoting more information in engaging and diverse formats via the project's website and social media during the upcoming phases of the project implementation.

Media content such as press releases, newsletters, videos and other multimedia items have been utilised on several occasions in order to promote FIERCE in varying target audiences. In correlation to the aforementioned need for increased efforts for online promotion due to the current conditions, media content is going to be used in a systematic way to disseminate the upcoming developments of the project.

During the second year of the project, a feminist summer school is scheduled to take place, based on our GA obligations. Our communication strategy to promote the event will utilize our online channels and tools, including website articles, social media posts, tailored visuals, press releases, etc. The knowledge produced from the summer school will also be disseminated via various channels and tools.

In addition, partners involved in *D1.1* and *D2.1* are preparing to publish the reports in two books. Our participation in conferences and other dissemination events will continue for the remain of the project duration.

In the third and final year of the project, a final Dissemination conference will be held, incorporating knowledge produced from all FIERCE activities. The communication of the event, utilizing all our channels and tools, is expected to attract significant attendance and raise awareness about the project and its results.

Overall, efforts will be made to continue and enhance synergies with sister projects but also identify other relevant project and establish communication channels as well as expand our community of engaged stakeholders.

The activities in which partners contributed presenting FIERCE and its results have played an important role in raising awareness about the main scope of the project. The organisation of a dedicated project co-creation activities and the participation of partners in events like third party workshops and/or conferences have secured that the project works appropriately on promoting its scope and generates knowledge for the identified target audiences. As the project proceeds and significant developments derive from Consortium's efforts, partners will have even more resources at their disposal in order to organise their own FIERCE events, as well as to participate in external events, thus producing additional presentations about the FIERCE outcomes.

In correlation to the above actions, the project has leveraged an extended network of Sister-Projects on gender equality to maximise the reach of its promotional activities and contribute to a great joint effort to foster gender equality in research and innovation in scientific fields. Following the spirit of synergy

among EU funded actions, FIERCE has been an active node within a network of completed, currently running and newly introduced European projects. As a result, the project has managed to actualise many dissemination opportunities and build collaboration ties with other projects. This asset is going to be valuable in terms of disseminating FIERCE's outcomes towards expert audiences who can facilitate their sustainability and further uptake.

Furthermore, FIERCE partners have already managed to extend the promotion of the project in local media (see Denmark for example). Such actions have a positive impact on the project's communication efforts towards a general public audience that consists of the societies in partners' countries. These interviews have paved the way for more partners to follow this example and share the project's vision with their respective societies using local and/or national outlets.

Annex 1: KPIs Monitoring

Status of the Communication KPIs (M18)

Activity	KPIs (Grant Agreement)	Achievements <u>by M18</u>
[C1] Project Identity and Branding	Templates for project documents, reports and presentations	YES
[C2] Dissemination Materials	1 brochure, 1 poster (eng. & national languages)	ALL materials in English and national languages
[C3] Project Website	250 monthly views (Y1), 500 monthly views (Y2) 24 blogs (Y2)	3 K web visitors, 12 K page views 30 blogs (M18)
[C4] Social Media Strategy	Y2: 2 posts/week (Twitter: 700 followers, Facebook: 500 Likes and LinkedIn: 300 followers)	Twitter: 155 posts, 202 followers Facebook: 120 posts, 194 likes, 211 followers LinkedIn: 127 posts, 303 followers
[C5] Videos/Podcasts	>3 project videos / >8 podcasts (1 x country on pilot actions) >300 views per YouTube video 500 >actual listens to each podcast episode	2 videos available 1 Podcast
[C6] Networking Events	>30 networking activities are foreseen during the project's lifetime	23
[C7] Generating positive coverage media	>30 articles; >15 interviews; >12 press releases, >6 E-Newsletters, 4 publications, 10 scientific publications	4 E-Newsletters 3 Press Releases 2 Publications 1 interview

Table 12: Status of Communication KPIs (M18)

Status of the Dissemination KPIs (M18)

Activity	KPIs (Grant Agreement)	Achievements by M18
[D1] Scientific Publications, Conferences & Workshops // Participation in events	>10 Open Access scientific papers published 1 Open Access co-edited volume >65 participants involved in the final conference	2 papers published 2 open access books under preparation
[D2] Other Open access publications policy briefs	1 toolkit and 3 policy briefs in 8 languages	1 policy brief in ENG
[D3] FIERCE Labs & Democratic innovations pilot actions; Feminist Summer School	> 150 participants in the 3 cycles of Co-creation Labs in 8 countries > 80 participants to each Transnational Labs online session 65 participants involved in the Transnational Network > 16 grassroots organizations partnering the innovation actions in 8 countries > 25 participants to the Feminist Summer School > 500 users of the online course created disseminate the feminist Summer School	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Total participants to national lab meetings: first co-creation cycle (129), second co-creation cycle (112). 2. Total participants to the transnational lab meetings: 26 to each session. In both meetings participants were distributed 21 from national labs and 5 from European feminist organisations (some of the participants changed between the two meetings). 3. Participants to the first FIERCE online roundtable (registered people 116 and between 65-60 attendees).
[D4] Synergies/ Clustering	15 project synergies	4 synergies

Table 13: Status of Dissemination KPIs (M18)

Status of the Exploitation KPIs (M18)

Activity	KPIs (Grant Agreement)	Achievements by M18
[E1] Conceptual Framework of feminism and antifeminism movement Analysis	Develop a framework to analyse social movements >8 case studies analysis Develop bottom-up participatory events >Organisation of 24 national-level events, 6 Transnational level ones (3 online and 3 face to-face)	16 national-level events 3 Transnational level ones (1 online and 2 F2F)
[E2] Transnational Network (T5.1)	Develop an active community of stakeholders >Involvement of 65 organisations/individuals	N/A yet
[E3] Policy Toolkit (D5.3)	Develop a framework for effective engendered policies	N/A yet
[E4] FIERCE's training material	Recorded modules from the Feminist Summer School exploit in other trainings and capacity building >3 trainings organised	N/A yet
[E5] FIERCE's Lessons Learnt	Expanding the outcomes beyond the end of the project	Continuous work

Table 14: Status of Exploitation KPIs (M18)

